

THE MODERN PRINCIPLE OF TREATMENT OF HYPOTHYROIDISM IN PEOPLE OF DIFFERENT AGE GROUPS

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Annotation

Hypothyroidism is an urgent problem of modern medicine. According to WHO, hypothyroidism ranks second in the world after diabetes mellitus, due to persistent deficiency of thyroid hormones or a decrease in their biological effect at the tissue level.

Key words: thyroid gland, thyroid hormones, hypothyroidism, treatment.

Introduction. The thyroid gland is an endocrine gland that plays an important role in the human body. It is involved in the production of thyroid hormones, these hormones are necessary to maintain normal metabolism in the human body. A huge number of scientific articles and monographs have been published in this important area of medicine, which indicates the constant significant interest of researchers in the problems of human health associated with the endocrine system in general, and the thyroid gland in particular [1, 2, 3, 4].

There is no need to talk about the relevance of the problem of hypothyroidism in the clinical practice of doctors of all specialties. Hypothyroidism is one of the most common diseases of the endocrine system. Hypothyroidism is diagnosed with hypofunction of the thyroid gland. In the absence of effective and proper treatment, this disease can lead to serious adverse health consequences and, ultimately, death [5]. All over the world, iodine deficiency is a very common cause of thyroid

diseases - hypothyroidism [6]. In areas with sufficient iodine, the most common cause of hypothyroidism is autoimmune thyroiditis (Hashimoto's disease). All organs and tissues in the human body are targets for thyroid hormones, which explains the variety of manifestations of hypothyroidism. Hypothyroidism has the most significant effect on the nervous, cardiovascular system and musculoskeletal system [7].

According to the pathogenesis, primary hypothyroidism is distinguished (developed during the pathology of the thyroid gland itself) and secondary (due to a lack of thyroid-stimulating hormone in the body). It is not uncommon for adults to develop primary hypothyroidism. According to a source [8], the cause of primary hypothyroidism in most cases is chronic autoimmune thyroiditis, less often thyroid resection, radioactive iodine therapy and other factors. In these conditions, an irreversible deficiency of thyroid hormones develops. Other causes of hypothyroidism due to the destruction of the thyroid gland include thyroidectomy, therapy with radioactive iodine, external radiation during radiation therapy of malignant neoplasms outside the thyroid gland. Do not forget that the persistent nature of hypothyroidism can be judged no earlier than 6 months after such interventions [9].

The pathogenetic classification of hypothyroidism is presented as follows [10]:

1. Hypothyroidism caused by a violation of the embryonic development of the thyroid gland, in other words, congenital hypothyroidism: aplasia and hypoplasia of the thyroid gland.
2. Hypothyroidism with a decrease in the amount of functioning thyroid tissue, there are: postoperative hypothyroidism; postoperative hypothyroidism; autoimmune thyroiditis; hypothyroidism caused by a viral lesion of the thyroid gland; hypothyroidism against the background of other pathological processes.
3. Hypothyroidism caused by a violation of the synthesis of thyroid hormones: endemic goiter in regions of severe iodine deficiency; sporadic goiter with

hypothyroidism with defects in the biosynthesis of thyroid hormones at various biosynthetic levels; medicinal hypothyroidism thiamazole, propylthiouracil, pharmacological doses (more than 1000 mcg) of iodine, perchlorate, thiocyanate, etc.); goiter developed as a result eating food containing goitrogenic substances (goitrogens, strumogens).

According to a source [11], the risk of developing goiter increases in patients with a hereditary predisposition to thyroid diseases. The genetic component has been identified in many cases of HSV. Pathology can develop against the background of genetic abnormalities that disrupt the production of thyroid hormones. The cause of congenital hypothyroidism may be mutations of genes that lead to disorders of migration, laying or differentiation of the thyroid gland, defects in the biosynthesis of thyroid hormones (genes TTF1, TTF2, PAX-8, NIS, TPO, DEHAL1).

Materials and methods. The material for this review article is information published in scientific journals and sources: science, Scopus, ABNT, etc.

Results and discussion. To solve one of the urgent problems of thyroid disorders, research is being conducted to study both the pathogenesis of hypothyroidism itself and the causes of this disease.

Treatment of all types of hypothyroidism is lifelong. The only exception is hypothyroidism caused by the administration of any medications or substances that block the production of thyroid hormones (T3, T4). The goal of treatment of hypothyroidism is the stable normalization of TSH levels within the normal range (0.4—4.0 MMU/l). The main goal of the treatment of hypothyroidism is to restore the normal physiological functions of all organs and systems disrupted due to hypothyroidism. And with all forms of hypothyroidism (primary, secondary, tertiary), the basis of treatment is adequate replacement therapy with thyroid hormone preparations such as Eutirox. Levothyroxine (Eutirox) is the drug of

choice for hypothyroidism replacement therapy. Its difference from other drugs in this group is the ability to easily choose the right dosage: (25, 50, 75, 100, 125 or 150 mcg), which greatly facilitates the implementation of hypothyroidism replacement therapy and helps to restore the functions of the systems. The criterion for the adequacy of treatment is the disappearance of clinical and laboratory manifestations of hypothyroidism [12]. Various thyroid hormone preparations are available for replacement therapy, including synthetic T4, T3, a combination of both synthetic hormones and dried extracts of the thyroid gland of animals. It is recommended to take L-thyroxine orally once a day in maintenance doses of 75-150 mcg, depending on age, body mass index and taking into account individual properties. The initial dose for young or middle-aged patients is 100 mcg, orally once a day [13].

And dried animal thyroid preparations contain various amounts of T3 and T4 and should not be used unless the patient is already taking such medications and using them to maintain normal serum TSH levels. In secondary hypothyroidism, l-thyroxine should not be prescribed until normal cortisol secretion has been proven. Since, with primary hypothyroidism, the level of cholesterol in the blood serum is usually elevated; in secondary hypothyroidism, its increase is less pronounced [14]. Patients with hypothyroidism are recommended to: preventive admission (examination, consultation) by an endocrinologist; medical and pedagogical supervision in case of complications of the course of this disease [15].

Conclusion. During the review of scientific publications, it should be noted about significant research of its kind towards improving early and effective treatment methods, including the removal of many thyroid pathologies and the negative effect of hypothyroidism on other systems and organs. In summary, it can be stated that the attention of numerous scientists to this problem indicates its significant relevance and the need for further applied research in this area of medical science.

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